

Current Solutions and Future Trends for Robotic Prosthetic Hands

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Abstract

The desire for functional replacement of a missing hand is an ancient one. Historically, humans have replaced a missing limb with a prosthesis for cosmetic, vocational, or personal autonomy reasons. The hand is a powerful tool, and its loss causes severe physical and often mental debilitation. Technological advancements have allowed the development of increasingly effective artificial hands, which can improve the quality of life of people who suffered a hand amputation. Here, we review the state of the art of robotic prosthetic hands (RPHs), with particular attention to the potential and current limits of their main building blocks: the hand itself, approaches to decoding voluntary commands and controlling the hand, and systems and methods for providing sensory feedback to the user. We also briefly describe existing approaches to characterizing the performance of subjects using RPHs for grasping tasks and provide perspectives on the future of different components and the overall field of RPH development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Decades of research on robotic prosthetic hands (RPHs) have led to a paradoxical situation: On the one hand, the development of novel RPHs is among the most exciting fields of robotics (Piazza 2019), but on the other hand, the vast majority of amputee patients still use technologies that have changed little in almost half a century. However, this apparent discrepancy might seem less surprising when considering the immense challenge of developing a prosthetic that can mimic the functions of a hand. Indeed, the hand has one of the largest sensory representations in the brain, and grasping is among the most complex coordination tasks (1); the hand has both the highest density of mechanoreceptors in the human body (see the sidebar titled Skin Mechanoreceptors) and the largest number of degrees of freedom (DOFs); and the hand permits people to both experience the surrounding world and shape it.

The skin has four types of mechanoreceptors, which are sensitive to different stimuli and therefore involved in different sensory functions: Merkel disks (which sense skin indentation, fine touch, and texture perception), Ruffini capsules (which sense skin stretch), Pacinian corpuscles (which sense vibration), and Meissner corpuscles (which sense dynamic deformation and slipperiness). Merkel disks and Ruffini capsules are slow-adapting receptors, meaning that they fire continuously during tactile stimuli, with a firing rate related to the pressure applied in their receptive field. Pacinian corpuscles and Meissner corpuscles are fast-adapting receptors that respond mostly to changes in applied pressure or brief stimuli.

The challenges are multiple and intricate, and they can be overcome only by combining advanced mechatronic solutions for dexterous and highly sensorized robotic hands with new approaches for robust and effective interfaces with users' nervous systems to allow seamless natural–artificial integration. As such, several viable solutions can emerge from this multidimensional optimization problem.

Tremendous efforts have been made in the past 20 years on the quest for an RPH that is easy to wear, comfortable, and intuitive to control. The design of such a device can be considered a compromise among dexterity, robustness, and usability (2). In the past 5 years, another aspect has been proposed by researchers as an essential milestone: sensorization. Indeed, feedback systems can increase both the acceptability and the performance of the new generation of RPHs (3–5).

This review summarizes the main achievements in this field. In particular, after providing an overview of the existing neuroprostheses and their characteristics, we focus on four central aspects: (a) stable interfaces that enable a new connection with the nervous system to record neural signals and stimulate neural structures, (b) algorithmic strategies for decoding motor intentions, (c) RPH sensorization plus encoding strategies to convey somatosensory feedback, and (d) assessment methods to measure the efficacy of a given strategy or technology. Throughout the review, we keep a patient-centered perspective and ask ourselves, Does a novel approach significantly improve the subjects' quality of life? Is it easy to learn and natural to use? And does it improve their independence? On a technical aspect, our goal is to provide a critical view of the most advanced technologies and a perspective on future implementations of RPHs.

2. ROBOTIC HANDS

Following a limb amputation, three solutions are generally considered: passive cosmetic limbs (**Figure 1a**); mechanical hands, often with hooks (**Figure 1b**); and RPHs (**Figure 1c–g**). In a survey of below-elbow amputees from Sweden, the United Kingdom, and Canada (6), 53% of the respondents wore a cosmetic prosthesis, 13% used a hook, 4% used a cable hand, and 30% used a myoelectric RPH. Despite encouraging results in the late 1990s (7), hand transplantation (**Figure 1h**) encountered significant surgical and clinical difficulties (rejection

and immunosuppression); it has therefore been tested in only a few patients and is not yet considered one of the available options.

Figure 1 Examples of functioning hand replacement. (a) A personalized cosmetic hand solution (ITOP, Italy) provides a natural look. Photos reproduced with permission from ITOP and Procosil. (b) A body-powered prosthetic solution (Ottobock, Germany) is a common approach for people with an upper-limb amputation. Photo reproduced with permission from Ottobock. (c) An sEMG-based pattern recognition system (Gen2, Coapt, USA) allows grasp classification. Photo reproduced with courtesy of Coapt LLC, www.coaptengineering.com. (d) sEMG control and extracellular stimulation via an implanted FINE were used to convey sensory feedback for home-use applications. The implant was stable for more than five years, and home-use electrical stimulation for sensory feedback was investigated for up to 13 days (115). Pannel adapted from reference 115 (CC BY-SA 4.0). (e) Fully implanted myoelectric sensors provide stronger and more reliable signals that do not change with arm positioning, socket rotation, or sweating (106). Pannel adapted with permission from reference (106). (f) Six-DOF prosthetic hand control (i-Limb Ultra, Össur, Iceland) uses threshold-based sEMG control and cocontraction to switch between grasps. (g) Sensory feedback conveyed via intraneural TIMEs enables the encoding of objects' shape and stiffness (5). Pannel reproduced with permission © 2014 Lifehand 2 / Patrizia Tocci. (h) Hand transplantation is a promising technique which has not yet become a standard procedure due to several surgical and clinical difficulties. Pannel adapted with permission from reference (Bernardon et al. 2015).

Abbreviations: DOF, degree of freedom; FINE, flat interface nerve electrode; RPNI, regenerative peripheral nerve interface; sEMG, surface electromyography; TIME, transverse intrafascicular multichannel electrode.

The cosmetic solution is often used for the most distal amputations (e.g., fingers) but is not adapted for patients with a transradial amputation given the dramatic loss of functionality. Body-powered mechanical hooks, mainly with one-DOF control, are popular solutions thanks to their low price, light weight, and easy maintenance. This type of prosthesis is also well suited for high-intensity work due to the control robustness. Also, because the subject must move their shoulder to open and close the hook, these systems have inherent proprioception feedback (8). However, one of the major limitations of the hook solution is the low level of dexterity and nonanthropomorphic appearance. Body-powered hands have solved the anthropomorphic aspect while keeping the robustness of body-powered solutions (9). For example, Baril et al. (10) developed a programmable body-powered hand that can perform different grasp types using a mechanical selector that blocks the closing of one or more fingers. Nevertheless, this solution has its drawback as well: Because of their low mechanical efficiency, body-powered prostheses require large amounts of energy (from 33 N for a hook to 131 N for a hand) to produce a relatively low pinch force (15 N) (11). This could explain their high rejection rate by patients, which ranges between 16% and 66% depending on the survey and time period (12).

Here, we concentrate on RPHs because they potentially offer the most versatile, natural, and power-efficient replacement for amputated hands and could become the default solution for patients. We investigate the challenges in existing RPHs, considering both commercially available solutions (**Supplemental Table 1**) and those in the research phase (**Supplemental Table 2**).

Mimicking the biomechanics of a hand is not easy. Early prototypes (13) succeeded in designing fingers with skeleton-like structures, but biomimetic actuation was only recently properly implemented using muscle-like actuators (14). The challenge for RPH developers is to embed actuators, sensors, and electronic components into a prosthesis with the same size and weight as the replaced hand (13, 15, 16). Major system integration and miniaturization is necessary before these systems could be used by amputee patients.

Instead, underactuation is a widespread approach to simplify the mechanics while keeping reasonable dexterity. An underactuated system is one where the number of degrees of actuation (DOAs) is smaller than the number of DOFs (see $DOA/DOF < 1$ in **Supplemental Tables 1** and **2**). The passive (nonactuated) DOFs are exploited to adapt to the surface in contact, as suggested by the concept of morphological computation (17), and to enable a self-adjusting grip without the need to control each articulation. These systems reduce the number of motors needed in the RPH and therefore its complexity, weight, and price.

2.1 Existing RPHs

Numerous commercially available RPH solutions use underactuated mechanisms (**Supplemental Table 1**), including the Michelangelo prosthetic hand (Ottobock, Germany), the i-Limb Ultra (Össur, Iceland), the bebionic hand (Ottobock), and the VINCENTevolution 3 (Vincent Systems, Germany). Despite remarkable advances, there is still arguably a trade-off

between dexterity and weight in these solutions, with companies usually emphasizing one aspect or the other.

Many research groups are currently working on innovative solutions to tackle the dexterity/weight dilemma (18), such as the use of a monolithic 3D-printed soft material (19) or mechanical solutions to implement finger synergies via clutches (20). For example, Jing et al. (18) proposed an anthropomorphic RPH using only three motors that could achieve 13 grasp types while weighing only approximately 130 g.

The price of RPHs is an additional limiting factor for broader adoption by patients. With most advanced solutions costing \$10,000–20,000, many researchers advocate for cheaper solutions, particularly for emerging countries (e.g., 21).

Open source RPHs are an exciting alternative to dramatically reduce the cost of development and distribution. One particularly interesting aspect of such hands is simplified maintenance and repairs (using, e.g., 3D printing) that do not rely on specific suppliers. For example, Open Bionics (United Kingdom) commercializes solutions for transradial amputees (e.g., the medically certified Hero Arm) but also provides the source files for some of their designs, and e-NABLE (<https://enablingthefuture.org>) reports 8,000 recipients of their prosthetics, which were built by volunteers around the world. Open source RPHs also enable users to alter the design to meet their unique needs; for example, the Galileo Hand (22) allows easy customization of the types of movements and number of electromyography (EMG) electrodes.

Researchers are also working on better mechanical solutions to improve RPH dexterity. An underactuated hand prosthesis designed by Abayasiri et al. (23) has finger abduction and adduction to enable it to grasp larger objects, and an adaptive prosthetic hand designed by Yong et al. (24) adds DOFs in the palm with movable metacarpals. The Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) prosthetic hand (25) has an embedded camera and real-time object recognition, enabling the hand to be preshaped. Pneumatic artificial muscle (26) permits the development of light, compact solutions. Finally, biomimetic actuation is used for muscle-like actuators (14).

In addition to the hardware aspect, there are also innovations in RPH control and sensorization. Low-level controllers use information about the state of the device and eventually activate the actuation to meet the desired state imposed by the user's intentions. The choice of the state variable has a strong influence on how the device works. Position or speed can be read through encoders of each joint and controlled; these are straightforward approaches that have been used broadly in robotic applications. When the interaction of the hand with the external environment is of interest, more advanced control systems are implemented, such as torque or impedance control. Both approaches measure the force applied by the actuator, controlling it directly in the first case and simulating compliance in the second. Advanced control strategies enable complex manipulation and smoother gestures at the expense of a bulkier mechanical structure and a more complex control system. Therefore, enabling more sophisticated control requires integrated force and position sensors, which have been previously developed mainly to close the robotic control loop (27).

In summary, low-cost and light hands have flourished over the last few years. The race to simplify designs and reduce costs through 3D printing should not impact the dexterity of RPHs. For now, underactuated mechanisms are the best solution for RPHs and innovative designs based on synergy mechanisms or friction, the latter of which can help increase the number of DOAs without increasing the number of motors.

2.2. Perspectives

While rigid architectures are still the norm, there has been recent interest in the development of flexible systems that inherently permit safe robot–human interaction (28). Instead of using a rigid structure with mechanical joints, the compliant structures in soft designs enable them to bend continuously in any part. Since seminal work by Hirose & Ma (29), there have been several attempts to develop soft underactuated hand prostheses (30) and soft body-powered devices (8). These architectures combine the advantages of simple actuation with the performance of an adaptable hand. Recent studies have proved that soft manipulators could match the performance of rigid systems in many applications (31). Further investigations are necessary to determine whether soft architectures are viable solutions for larger use.

Innovative actuations systems such as McKibben pneumatic muscles, granular jamming (32), and electro-conjugate fluid (33), which are strongly tied to soft robotic devices, are another interesting direction. Soft RPHs have the advantage of exploiting the structure to embed and eventually improve sensorization, safety, and efficiency (e.g., 34). These systems are at the early stage and need massive integration before being deployed in portable devices.

3. INTERFACES WITH THE NEUROMUSCULAR SYSTEM

Decades of work on robotic prosthetics have led to numerous invasive and noninvasive solutions for interfacing with the body (for a review, see Yoshida 2017) (**Table 1**). Here, we describe existing technologies and outline the ones we consider the most promising for the future.

3.1 Taxonomy of the existing interfaces

To classify and evaluate the quality of an interface, selectivity—defined as the ability to record from a specific location within the nerve—is the most straightforward metric. Both spatial and temporal selectivity are important, naturally, as they enable better motor decoding and more localized sensory feedback. Electrode invasiveness, by contrast, is categorized into two large classes, surface electrodes and implanted electrodes, the latter of which includes extraneural (i.e., around the nerve) (35, 36), intraneural (i.e., through the nerve) (5), and regenerative approaches (where the nerve regrows inside the electrode) (37; for reviews, see 38, 39). Invasiveness is often seen as a trade-off to selectivity, with the observation that higher selectivity comes at the cost of greater invasiveness (40). While this relationship continues to be true to a large extent, two amendments are necessary: First, there are a multitude of other

dimensions to consider, and second, recent results are suggesting that the relationship might not be the same in the motor and the sensory domains. We detail both aspects here.

Table 1 Maturity levels of different technologies

Technology	Most widespread	Mature, home use	Cutting edge, laboratory use	Future directions
Interface	Body harness ^c	sEMG ^a iEMG (50) ^a Vibrotactile interface (176) ^b TENS ^b FINEs (135) ^b Osseointegration (137) ^c	HD-sEMG (177) ^a Regenerative electrodes (37) ^a TIMEs (5, 41) ^b LIFEs (42) ^b Sieve electrodes (178) ^b Utah Array (112) ^c	Noninvasive intraneural stimulation (ultrasound) ^b Soft neurotechnology (47) ^b
Motor decoding	Body power Threshold-based sEMG	EMG-based pattern recognition (e.g., Ottobock Myo Plus, Coapt Gen2)	Simultaneous single-finger classification (74) Linear regression and shared control (78)	Advanced control using regenerative peripheral nerve interfaces (37) Deep learning for single-finger proportional control
Sensory feedback	No feedback	Vibrotactile haptic feedback (128) Touch contact (137) Position (135)	Neuromorphic (61) Texture (60) Object stiffness (5) Multimodal (position and tactile) (63) Biomimetic stimulation (61)	Temperature feedback Proprioception
Sensorization	No skin	Force sensors (measuring motor current) Sensorized fingertips (e.g., bebionic)	Asynchronously coded electronic skin (124)	Soft embedded sensors (114) Bioinspired flexible organic artificial afferent nerve (121)

Abbreviations: EMG, electromyography; FINE, flat interface nerve electrode; HD-sEMG, high-density surface electromyography; iEMG, intramuscular EMG; LIFE, longitudinal intrafascicular electrode; sEMG, surface electromyography; TENS, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation; TIME; transverse intrafascicular multichannel electrode.

^aMotor interface.

^bSensory interface.

^cBoth motor and sensory interface.

Beyond the selectivity of an interface, it is crucial to consider its reach and level of discrimination. For example, transverse intrafascicular multichannel electrodes (TIMEs) (41) and longitudinal intrafascicular electrodes (LIFEs) (42) can have a very similar selectivity, but TIMEs reach a more substantial proportion of the nerve and therefore can infer more information about the whole signal. Comparing muscle stimulation with different electrodes,

Badia et al. (43) showed that a TIME could target three muscles, whereas they could not activate more than one muscle with a LIFE. Spatial discrimination of neural signals from nontarget signals is influenced not only by the electrode's invasiveness (how close it is to the source) but also by its geometry (e.g., a spherical point source targets a small volume), electrode material, and configuration (e.g., a cylindrical electrode better discriminates the axons perpendicular to the main axis) (44).

Signal quality and stability are also important aspects that have been extensively studied. Work in this area has included interventions to improve the device–tissue interfaces [e.g., electrode coating (45) or a hollow glass cone that permits the ingrowth of cortical neurites in the electrodes (46)], electrode impedance, and filtering processes to increase the signal-to-noise ratio. The recording stability depends on biocompatibility, the electrode's robustness (resistance to physical manipulation), and the stability of the contact between the interface and neural tissue. Significant efforts toward soft and implantable electrodes (47) have been made in order to reduce insertion trauma and physical mismatches between neural tissues and implantable interfaces. Finally, properly anchoring the electrodes with the neural tissues is also essential to maintain a steady recording or stimulation site over time. This is particularly important in the sensory domain, where the stability of the elicited sensation is paramount for continuous use.

Finally, practicalities such as the cost of the technology and the difficulty of the implant must be considered. As such, an implantation procedure based on a known surgical procedure (48) has a better chance to be accepted and adopted by surgeons. The use of existing devices, materials, and mature technologies is also a way to reduce costs and risks. An example of such strategy is the use of Utah Arrays, which use well-established electrodes for brain recording, to interface with the peripheral nervous system.

For motor decoding, surface EMG (sEMG) approaches are by far the most widely used technique to date. Recent implementations using a large number of electrodes [termed high-density sEMG (HD-sEMG) (49)] have shown unprecedented results in terms of accuracy and decoding robustness (for details, see Section 4). Implanted EMG (iEMG) has shown higher performance and stability than sEMG on the continuous control of three DOFs (50). However, studies have found no statistical difference in different electrodes' ability to differentiate among 12 types of grasps (51). Neural interfaces with the peripheral nerves have also shown promising results on grasp classification with TIMEs (52) and proportional control with a Utah Slanted Electrode Array (53). However, the development of real-time control and sensory feedback stimulation is still at an early stage (52, 53) and will need further investigation.

In the sensory domain, there is no current consensus for noninvasive approaches. Tactile feedback using vibrotactile (54, 55), mechanotactile (56), or sensory substitution [e.g., audio (57)] has been proposed. Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) is a viable noninvasive approach to induce close to natural sensation with amputee patients (58, 59). However, as detailed elsewhere in this review, current solutions using implanted electrodes (particularly intraneural interfaces) have shown levels of sensory recovery far superior to those of noninvasive approaches. This is true from a functional point of view [e.g., the

possibility to encode texture (60) or shapes and stiffness (5)], phenomenologically [patients perceive the feedback as close to natural (61)], and in terms of cognitive load (62).

3.2. Perspectives

The challenges for future interfaces that can provide the necessary read/write bandwidth to use RPHs in a natural fashion are immense. We argue that the motor and sensory domains raise different problems. Indeed, the stimulation being close to the target is mandatory with current technologies, and therefore the best solutions are the most invasive ones. In the motor domain, it is possible to decompose the signal if we have enough sources (even noninvasive sources, as with sEMG). As shown in Section 4, machine learning techniques can help infer information from noninvasive interfaces.

On the sensory level, the currently implantable electrodes are the most promising solution. However, the main advancement so far has been for the tactile modality, while the use of other modalities for proprioception has been obtained via a nonhomologous approach based on intraneural stimulation combined with the delivery of homologous tactile feedback via indirectly targeted intraneural electrical stimulation (63).

Temperature sensation is another limit. Temperature is mediated through A δ fibers (for cold) and C fibers (for warmth). Given the very small size of these fibers (C fibers are 20–100 times smaller than A β fibers), it is not possible to target them using existing state-of-the-art electrodes (41). Future electrodes with even higher levels of selectivity might be able to target A δ and C fibers. Sensory remapping (64) can be another viable solution to simulate temperature feedback on a different part of the body using a temperature display.

4. MOTOR CONTROL

Despite the advances in techniques for voluntary motor decoding and the increased sophistication of the available RPHs, body-powered prostheses are still the most robust control approach. The mechanism of these devices is based on a cable actuated by movements of the shoulder to control one DOF. The vast majority of commercially available RPHs use simple threshold-based sEMG decoding over a few surface electrodes and also generally control one DOF (65); in some cases, the RPH provides more DOFs, but this comes at the cost of a nonintuitive command scheme. These systems also offer no possibility to control several DOFs at the same time. The current situation is, therefore, increasingly sophisticated RPH mechanics with unchanged control strategies. As such, patients often abandon myoelectric prostheses, in part because the small functional improvement does not justify their price and complexity (12, 66).

Here, we describe recent advances in control strategies in terms of decoding type (classification or continuous control) and functional achievement (e.g., number of DOFs, grasping, or single-finger decoding) and compare them with the classical direct control approach. Section 4.1 details different algorithmic approaches to decode motor functions,

with an emphasis on sEMG; Section 4.2 discusses the addition of robotic automation to improve grasp robustness; Section 4.3 compares implanted methods to extract the user's intentions; and finally, Section 4.4 presents a perspective on the broader adoption of these techniques by patients. **Table 1** includes the different decoding strategies and their level of maturity.

4.1. Decoding Algorithms

The clinical standard for RPH control is based on the use of two sEMG channels, with the electrodes placed superficially on antagonist muscles. The envelope of the signal is extracted so that the user can control the closing and opening of the RPH by modulating the amplitude of their muscle contraction. When the amplitude exceeds a certain threshold, the RPH will move depending on which muscle was activated. Companies are offering more DOFs, using cocontraction to cycle through different types of grasps (e.g., Ottobock's Michelangelo hand). However, this type of control is highly nonintuitive and gives only low dexterity to the user. An alternative to this direct control approach is based on pattern recognition methods, extracting hand-crafted features to characterize the signal in a discriminative way (e.g., the signal root mean square, wavelength, and zero crossing) and classify the type of grasp intended by the user. This solution has become robust enough to reach the market (the Coapt system and Ottobock's Myo Plus). Using 2–12 bipolar sEMG electrodes makes it possible to obtain good classification rates for different kinds of grasps, with 90–95% accuracy for 4–12 classes and up to 75% for 50 classes (67–71).

Using a similar electrode disposition and classification method, other groups showed the possibility of decoding single-finger movement using the classification of flexion or extension (72, 73). Recently, Bhagwat & Mukherji (74) showed single- and multifinger classification of 15 different movements with 99.79% accuracy. Researchers are also working on proportional control instead of classification, which makes it possible to decode several DOFs (e.g., wrist and finger movements) simultaneously and proportionally (75, 76). This type of control offers continuous position control. Several studies have also shown that single-finger proportional control is feasible, with good results (77, 78).

As an alternative, nonbiomimetic EMG decoders have been developed that rely on the subject learning inverse maps to relate motor outputs to arbitrary control variables (79). Using an abstract decoding cursor control space, subjects can learn to modulate their EMG activity to reach different targets arranged in a center-out task in order to trigger various grasping movements (80). Dyson et al. (81) recently validated these results on amputee participants; they showed that after training, the difficulty of the tasks could be increased, improving the possibilities for robotic hand control.

With only a few electrodes placed on muscles of interest, the accurate positioning of the electrodes requires anatomical knowledge; indeed, the type of amputation (congenital or traumatic), the surgical procedure, and the time since amputation (82) could influence the muscle anatomy and make the placement of the electrode tedious and specific to individual subjects. Moreover, a small shift in electrode placement can disrupt the pattern recognition

algorithm (83). To tackle these issues, several authors have proposed HD-sEMG as an alternative solution, which consists of a grid of closely spaced electrodes. The large number of electrodes allows information to be recorded from a large part of the subject's forearm.

HD-sEMG signals offer high spatial resolution, and recorded signals can be interpreted as spatial images of EMG activity. Using this image representation of EMG data, HD-sEMG is robust to small electrode shifts (84). Boschmann & Platzner (84) used a structural similarity index, borrowed from the computer vision field, on HD-sEMG images combined with a simple one-against-one nearest-neighbor classifier to decode wrist and hand motions. Similarly, Stango et al. (85) used a variogram of images (a measure of the degree of spatial correlation, used mainly in geostatistics) to classify wrist movements. Both groups showed that their methods, which use spatial information from the images, performed better or similarly to the classic feature extraction approach. Moreover, their strategies improved the robustness to electrode shift and electrode number. The use of several spatially close electrodes makes it possible to decompose the EMG signal into its constituent motor unit action potential (49, 86). Kapelner et al. (87) investigated this approach, decomposing EMG signals to extract motor unit activity from forearm muscles during wrist motions. Recently, Dai & Hu (88) showed that an approach consisting of finger joint angle estimation, combining classification for finger selection with EMG decomposition into motor unit activity, outperforms a standard amplitude-based approach.

We observe a paradigm shift from feature engineering to feature learning using raw data as input for deep neural networks. Studies have shown that combining this deep learning approach with HD-sEMG offers better performance than hand-crafted features in both grasp classification (89) and simultaneous single-finger and wrist movement classification (90). Deep learning has also shown good results with a smaller number of electrodes for grasp classification (71) and regression of arm or wrist motions (91, 92).

This approach permits both high dexterity and robustness, with unprecedented performance. However, one of the major difficulties of the deep learning approach is that it requires an extensive data set for training. For example, the deep learning used for the ImageNet challenge in 2012 used 1.2 million images for training on 1,000 categories (93). In the context of hand gesture recognition, generating tens of thousands of examples for a subject is not a viable option.

A possible solution could use domain adaptation [often called transfer learning in the EMG literature (94, 95)], by leveraging data acquired from several subjects to enhance and accelerate training for a new user. Indeed, the aim is to use information from a database of several source domains and adapt it to a target domain (the end user) with a small number of samples. Authors generally apply deep domain adaptation (domain adaptation combined with deep learning) by pretraining a deep neural network and fine-tuning it with a few repetitions of movements by a target subject. The main idea is that gathering the recordings of several participants can meet the necessary conditions to learn a general mapping of all users' sEMG signals.

Using this idea, Côté-Allard et al. (96) showed that their deep model was able to learn the features and significantly enhance the performance of deep networks on out-of-sample gestures. Using HD-sEMG and deep learning, Du et al. (97) also showed an unsupervised deep domain adaptation method that incrementally learns from data during a new session without explicit calibration of gestures. Consequently, deep learning offers a particularly attractive context from which to develop deep domain adaptation algorithms to leverage interuser data. This approach can increase decoding performance, improve robustness to electrode shift, and reduce the number of repetitions needed during training (98).

As seen in this section, the search for new EMG decoding algorithms that go beyond threshold-based detection is an active field of research. Phinyomark & Scheme (99) and Khamparia & Singh (100) have reviewed recent research in EMG pattern recognition methods.

Machine learning in the field of computer vision and object recognition has shown outstanding results using deep learning and is already used commercially by many companies. Some deep learning algorithms based on a pretrained network are now usable without any fine-tuning (e.g., self-driving cars). However, bio-signals are intrinsically different from images and need adaptation. More important, the amount of labeled EMG data available to effectively train deep networks might not be sufficient to capture the evolution of the signal over time (electrode displacement, skin impedance changes, etc.). Therefore, if model architectures and data processing are tailored for bio-signal applications and take into consideration signal evolution with time, deep learning can become a solution for more robust motor intention decoding.

4.2. Shared Control to Help Motor Decoding

The ultimate goal of RPH control is to be as close as possible to controlling a natural hand. Therefore, an ideal control needs to be intuitive and continuous over individual fingers and wrist movements. Increasing the number of DOFs and developing proportional control will increase dexterity for prosthesis users but will inevitably reduce the overall robustness of the decoder. Since reliability is one of the main factors for upper-limb prosthesis users (101), this is a significant issue for the commercialization of more dexterous control schemes.

One possible solution to improve decoding robustness is to add robotic automation of some portion of the motor command. Shared-control strategies between a subject and a smart robotic hand have been reported for automated preshaping and grasping (102), grip force adjustment (103), slip detection, and hand closing (104). In the context of single-finger proportional control, Zhuang et al. (78) proposed a shared-control strategy to increase grasp robustness (avoiding accidental drops), by maximizing the number of contacts between the RPH and an object while allowing the user to maintain full autonomy over decisions about grasping and releasing, grasp preshaping, and non-grasp-related motions. These strategies allow both freedom during single-finger control and robustness during a grasp event (78) and can perform more dexterous movements that cannot be decoded based on EMG alone. However, they necessitate many DOAs (e.g., active control of each phalanx to reposition the

fingers around an object), which is still a significant challenge in terms of motor miniaturization, power consumption, and cost.

4.3. Decoding Motor Intention via Implanted Electrodes

Surface electrodes cannot precisely record the signal from deep muscles; to overcome this issue, several groups have focused on iEMG electrodes. This technique is more invasive but allows one to record EMG signals (50) uncorrelated from the underlying musculature and avoids the daily placement of electrodes. iEMG is robust against electrode shift (e.g., socket rotation) and change in skin impedance and sweat. Several studies have demonstrated the performance of simultaneous wrist and hand motions (three DOFs) using six to eight iEMG electrodes; Smith & Hargrove (50) showed that iEMG has better decoding performance than sEMG. High decoding performance is reported in real time (105), and in fully implanted setups, the results are stable for several days (106).

On the other hand, Farrell & Weir (51) compared the pattern recognition–based grasp classification performance of iEMG and sEMG on 12 movement classes with eight channels and did not find a statistical difference between electrode types. They concluded that the choice of electrode should be based not on classification accuracy but rather on signal consistency over time and robustness to electrode lift-off. Zia ur Rehman et al. (107) compared a standard linear discriminant analysis with a deep network for grasp classification. They performed a multiday analysis comparing six iEMG and six sEMG electrodes, and their results showed that deep learning had better decoding performance and was more stable over time.

Kamavuako et al. (108) investigated the effect of combining iEMG to target deep muscles with sEMG on myoelectric control. They showed that the combined solution improved offline and real-time control performance compared with sEMG alone.

With 32 iEMG electrodes, Dantas et al. (109) compared different decoding methods for the continuous control of five DOFs corresponding to the flexion and extension of each digit. Using a data set aggregation algorithm, they showed a normalized mean squared error as low as 0.033 with a deep convolutional neural network. They also investigated signal stability during 150 days after training, showing a small degradation during the first month (0.003 normalized mean squared error per day with a convolutional neural network), but that degradation stopped in the next four months.

For transradial amputees, an alternative to using EMG signals to control hand prostheses is decoding from peripheral nerve signals. Different grasp types can be decoded from peripheral nerve signals with high accuracy using different interfaces, both offline and in real time (53, 110–112). Implanted peripheral nerve recordings are more invasive than sEMG but are more stable over time. Indeed, donning and doffing the prosthesis does not move these electrodes as much as it does sEMG electrodes. Recently, Cracchiolo et al. (52) decoded up to 11 class states using TIMEs on an amputee subject and showed that the active sites chosen on the first day could also be used in the following sessions, for up to seven days (80% accuracy, compared with 83% by selecting active sites every session). However, this modality is generally

used to provide sensory feedback (63, 113–115). Therefore the development of new approaches to record neural signals during peripheral stimulation [e.g., artifact removal (116)] is necessary.

Vu et al. (37) recently developed a regenerative peripheral nerve interface to increase signal specificity and long-term stability. They implanted transected peripheral nerves into a free muscle graft. After regeneration, revascularization, and reinnervation, the graft becomes a nerve bioamplifier that creates EMG signals. Using chronically implanted iEMG to record from these grafts, they performed five-class decoding in real-time with up to 98.2% accuracy with two transradial amputees in a virtual hand environment. They also showed results from a Box and Block Test using a robotic hand prosthesis that provided continuous control of two DOFs of thumb motions through their interface combined with a third DOF based on sEMG.

4.4. Perspectives

Motor decoding for RPHs is progressing in two main directions: Noninvasive approaches have seen advances in decoding algorithms using large data sets and increases in the number of recording points, and implanted electrodes (either muscular or intraneural) have seen improvements that enable better recording stability and more robust decoding. There is currently no consensus on which approach is best for transradial amputee patients, as they each have their own strengths and limitations. The need for daily signal and classification recalibration is a weak point of the classic sEMG approach, which is being addressed by several research groups developing, for example, HD-sEMG. And despite iEMG's promising control performance, which is robust to donning and doffing of the prosthesis, its overall performance gain, when compared with sEMG, may not currently be sufficient to justify an invasive surgery. The same reasoning can be applied to intraneural electrodes.

One can imagine a future where both invasive and noninvasive approaches will continue to progress and will target either patients who prefer a stable decoding setup or those who do not want to undergo surgery and will accept the need to calibrate their prosthesis on a regular basis (117). Another scenario can be a parallel development of invasive technologies for both sensory and motor functions. Indeed, as shown in Section 5, the approach using intraneural implanted electrodes has permitted unprecedented levels of somatosensory restoration; it might, therefore, be reasonable to perform a single surgery to restore both motor and sensory functions. For this reason, motor decoding using the intraneural interface can become a viable solution if these interfaces one day permit both providing sensory feedback and recording discriminative signals for motor decoding in parallel, but online artifact removal remains an important challenge.

Power consumption is another critical issue: RPHs should embed small electronics because the size of the prosthesis limits the space available for batteries, but doing so usually comes at the cost of limited processing resources. Also, the electronics for the HD-sEMG remain cumbersome due to the large number of input channels and should be miniaturized and portable. Moreover, decoding model complexity is also limited by portable processing resources. In practice, an increased number of electrodes is already available in wearable

systems (Sessantaquattro, OT Bioelettronica, Italy) and may become available for prostheses in the future.

Finally, low latency is paramount for seamless prosthesis control [<300 ms between user intention and real-time decoding (118)]. Among the studies discussed above, only a few performed analyses to show the feasibility of real-time control (without processing resource limitations), and even fewer included embedded electronics that would translate for home use. One possible solution for real-time decoding with complex models is to bypass embedded electronic limitations; this could be achieved by taking advantage of the computational power of cell phones or by relying on cloud computing and the next generations of wireless cellular networks for low-latency communication.

5. RESTORING SENSORY FEEDBACK

Sensory information plays a critical role in both the exploration of the external environment and in any manipulation task. When an individual interacts with surrounding objects, tactile sensations are used to infer features such as size, compliance, temperature, and texture, while the same sensations are exploited to handle them properly or use them as tools. From this perspective, aiming to restore afferent sensory channels from a hand prosthesis is a critical step in designing a device that ensures two key aspects: dexterous manipulation and embodiment of the prosthetic device.

The design of a sensory feedback system that can successfully deliver information relies on three fundamental blocks working together: (*a*) sensor readings, processed by (*b*) an encoding strategy capable of translating meaningful information to the user, through (*c*) an interface. Previous sections have described the different available interfaces; here, we present the encoding techniques and sensors relevant to the design of modern hand prostheses (**Table 1**).

Sensors mounted on a robotic hand should ideally record the whole spectrum of available human sensations, from both external and internal sources. Indeed, sensory information from the human hand covers both interactions with the external world (tactile perception, thermal perception, and nociception, i.e., perception of pain) and internal perception of the positions of the joints and the length and forces exerted by the muscles, together known as proprioception. **Table 2** shows examples of sensor placements on RPHs from recent studies.

5.1. Sensors for Proprioception

Proprioception is not only fundamental for a dexterous hand prosthesis, enabling vision-free manipulation and multitasking, but is also the key to a properly embodied device (63).

Usually, kinematic parameters of the robotic hand and (when available) the force exerted are needed to implement low-level control of the actuators, so they are measured with well-established systems, such as rotary encoders or the motor's current draw.

Table 2 Sensor types and encoding strategies used in milestone publications on bidirectional hand prostheses

Reference	RPH model	Mechanical stimulation encoding	Electrical stimulation encoding			Interface	Sensor distribution ^a
			Frequency	Amplitude	Pulse width		
3	Passive	Linear	—	—	—	G10 tactor	
5	IH2 Azzurra	—	Fixed	Linear	Fixed	TIME	
59	IH2 Azzurra	—	Fixed	Fixed	Linear	TENS	
61	IH2 Azzurra	—	Model based	Model based	Fixed	TIME	
36	SensorHand Speed	—	Linear	Fixed	Time variant	FINE	
60	IH2 Azzurra	—	Neuromorphic	Fixed	Fixed	TIME	
128	Various	Discrete events	—	—	—	Vibrators	
135	VariPlus Speed	—	Linear	Fixed	Fixed	FINE	
58	bebionic	—	Neuromorphic	Fixed	Neuromorphic	TENS	
63	IH2 Azzurra	—	Fixed	Fixed	Linear	TIME	
138	DEKA Luke	—	Model based	Fixed	Fixed	Utah Slanted Electrode Array	

137	SensorHand Speed	—	Linear	Fixed	Fixed	Cuff electrode	
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Abbreviations: FINE, flat interface nerve electrode; RPH, robotic prosthetic hand; TENS, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation; TIME; transverse intrafascicular multichannel electrode.

^aThe positions of the pressure sensors are shown in green, the joints where force is measured are shown with solid red lines, and the joints where the position is read are shown with blue dashed lines.

5.2. Tactile Sensors

Despite improvements in sensor miniaturization, computational power, and knowledge of the neurophysiology of somatosensation (tactile sensation and proprioception), the capabilities of sensorized RPHs remain far from those of a natural hand. Overcoming this limitation will require satisfying three conditions: The sensors must match the skin’s sensing ability, a sufficient number of sensors must be embedded on the surface of the hand, and it must be possible to reliably read information from them. The first condition can be addressed with current technology, as the resolution of existing force and pressure sensors already matches human skin performance (119). However, fulfilling the second and third conditions is another matter, and we need to push the boundaries of circuit integration in order to create an RPH with many sensors and a way to communicate with them.

The classical solution of using general-purpose sensors developed separately from the signal conditioning circuit and the subsequent signal processing has shown its limit. Instead, efforts are being made to optimize these devices with prosthetics in mind. For example, borrowing the concept of morphological computation from robotics (120), sensors can be optimized for specific tasks by tuning the features of their mechanical structures accordingly. Indeed, exploiting the low-pass filtering effect of a compliant material or surfaces with specific structures can increase texture discrimination (60, 114). Another example comes from Kim et al. (121), who measured forces using sensors embedded in a soft substrate.

5.3. Sensory Architectures

The problem of handling many sensors at the same time has been addressed successfully in the past by using time-sharing (multiplexing) and space-sharing (matrix arrangement) techniques, minimizing wiring complexity while keeping read latency in an acceptable range. Nevertheless, this approach does not scale well in terms of covering the whole hand with a sensor density comparable to that of the human hand. Additionally, the unavoidable increase in the number of electrical connections makes the system highly susceptible to breakage.

Event-based architectures rely on the concept of send-on-delta (122), where each sensor (comprising an analog front end and an analog-to-digital converter), instead of signaling its value at a constant rate, does so only when the value changes by more than a certain threshold. These architectures have many advantages owing to the sparsity of the data

representation. In other words, the communication line does not need to be capable of handling all the sensors simultaneously (as an interaction where all the sensors are triggered in the same moment is unlikely); instead, single sensors are polled at a high rate, which preserves the time structure of the stimulus.

The underlying idea of event-based systems is inspired by how neurons communicate information to each other, sending a train of spikes instead of continuous value. In earlier implementations, data flowed from sensors to the central unit through digital communication lines using well-known protocols such as Universal Asynchronous Transmitter Receiver (UART), Ethernet, and the Controller Area Network (CAN) bus. Some groups have designed communication paradigms by mimicking information encoding by the nerves; using pulses of 20 ns, Bartolozzi et al. (123) showed a 94% improvement in data rate over traditional protocols.

An even more advanced step was made in the work of Lee et al. (124), where the sensors communicate with spikes through the same conductive surface without any flow control, reducing the wires needed to two (data and ground). In this way, at the cost of a decoding stage for sensor value acquisition, the performance of the architecture increased, reaching up to 100,000 sensors sharing the same bus.

5.4. Sensory Feedback

In basic myoelectric or body-powered prostheses, feedback is delivered mainly by visually inspecting the movements of the prosthesis and by the physical interaction between the device and the user (125), as with hook prostheses. Clearly, the goal of a modern, robotic hand prosthesis is to deliver richer information more intuitively.

Sensory feedback strategies are characterized by their precision and the coherence between the evoked sensation and the desired one in terms of timing (synchronicity), position (somatotopy) and modality (i.e., touch, vibration, and temperature). Feedback techniques encode sensor values to stimulation parameters, which in turn are strongly tied to the chosen stimulation interface (**Table 2**). Here, we focus mainly on electrical interfaces for feedback, but we also briefly discuss the mechanical interfaces.

Noninvasive feedback strategies are attractive approaches since they do not necessitate surgical interventions (**Figure 2a**). Starting with the Boston Arm, which Mann & Reimers (126) used to demonstrate that position feedback was needed for precise reaching movements, these techniques have improved in both mechanical and electrical interfaces with the user. Indeed, the intact mechanoreceptors in the skin of the arm can be stimulated with small linear (127) or vibrating (128) motors that vary in their driving amplitude and frequency. On the other hand, mechanical stimulation brings an unavoidable delay of approximately 400 ms in the delivery of the sensation (129), and the integration and miniaturization of mechanoreceptors are challenging. The miniaturization of noninvasive feedback approaches is also challenging.

Figure 2 A neural interface and the target area for somatosensory feedback. (a) Noninvasive strategies include tactors targeting Meissner corpuscles and encoding pressure (3), vibrators that activate Pacinian corpuscle mechanoreceptors (128), and TENS (58), which targets the nerve noninvasively. (b) Invasive peripheral nervous system stimulation can be done with cuff electrodes (137) or FINEs (36, 135) that stimulate the nerve from outside the fiber. TIMEs (5, 59, 60, 63, 179) and Utah Slanted Electrode Arrays (180) are more invasive and are inserted through the nerve but stimulate directly from inside the fiber. (c) Epidural stimulation of the lateral spinal cord at the cervical level was able to induce tactile sensation in three upper-arm amputees (139). Abbreviations: FINE, flat interface nerve electrode; TENS, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation; TIME, transverse intrafascicular multichannel electrode. Nerve design from panels (a) and (b) adapted with permission from reference (41).

Electrical stimulation is usually delivered as train pulses, of which width, amplitude, and frequency can be independently modulated and can be conveyed noninvasively through the skin; this technique is generally known as electrotactile feedback (130). Single electrotactile electrodes can be assembled in bands and arrays (131) for targeting multiple sites at the same time, encoding information in both the position and amplitude of the stimulation. The main drawbacks of electrotactile stimulation are the dependence of sensory thresholds on the stimulation position (130), which forces a calibration after each mounting, and the artifacts induced in EMG readings, which strongly impair its application in closed-loop RPHs.

Electrocutaneous stimulation tries to overcome electrotactile limitations by implanting subdermally thin electrodes. Geng et al. (132) characterized the sensations evoked and highlighted improvements in the detection threshold, the threshold of noticeable differences, and the general pleasantness compared with traditional electrotactile feedback. Electrocutaneous stimulation still has technical issues in real-world implementations, such as interference with EMG readings and variability in stimulation parameters over time (133), which impair long-term applications.

Feedback through neural electrodes is a promising modality that matches how sensory information is transmitted in the nervous system (**Figure 2b**). These electrodes are implemented at both the cortical (134) and peripheral levels. Here, we focus on techniques targeting the peripheral nervous system.

The three controlled parameters are the frequency, amplitude, and pulse width; the most straightforward approach is proportional modulation according to sensor readings. Studies have shown that this method can be successful even in long-term implants (113, 135–137) and confirmed the improvements brought by sensory feedback through peripheral nervous system interfaces in both performance and embodiment.

Compared with noninvasive approaches, invasive neural stimulation has the advantage of being able to elicit sensations intuitive for the user, as they are delivered through the expected biological route (the peripheral nervous system) for sensory feedback. The focus in this field is currently shifting from basic feedback to evoking complex and natural sensations, feeding high-level features such as texture (60), and in general exploiting the potential of stimulating the nerves directly. Noninvasive feedback strategies are limited in the spatial precision of the evoked sensation in both mechanical and electrical stimulation (59).

The naturalness and information content of the stimulation can be improved by modulating with patterns that go beyond a simple relation with the sensor value. George et al. (138) devised two biomimetic stimulation patterns: one that is proportional to the first derivative of the force and another that is proportional to the aggregated tactile nerve response. Both approaches outperformed standard modulation techniques and were felt to be more informative by the user. Valle et al. (61) started from a model of the response to the touch of human afferent fibers and modulated frequency and amplitude according to a simulated fire rate and fiber recruitment; at the cost of a small reduction in sensitivity, the user reported a consistent increase in the naturalness of the sensation together with an increase in dexterity during functional evaluations. Both of these studies highlighted that the

goal is not only to elicit precise sensations but also to focus on naturalness and intuitiveness. Neuromorphic stimulation patterns have also proven to be rich in information not only about tactile contact but also about the sliding speed and texture of an object (114).

Considering the complex surgical procedure and the effort needed to develop a peripheral nervous system interface, techniques based on spinal cord stimulation are promising, as they rely on devices that have already been tested and approved by the US Food and Drug Administration. Chandrasekaran et al. (139) recently demonstrated a sensory neuroprosthetic for amputee subjects with spinal cord stimulation (**Figure 2c**). The main issue with this approach is the difficulty of eliciting natural sensations; biomimetic stimulation approaches could help address this limitation in the future.

5.5. Perspectives

We believe that sensorization will play a significant role in the next generation of RPHs. Here, we discuss three main directions influenced by sensorization: embedded sensorization, improved stimulation strategies, and new computational architectures.

5.5.1. Embedded sensorization.

Sensorized hands are not yet prevalent in the literature but are starting to draw interest, especially with the improvement of interfaces for bidirectional prostheses (for a list of RPHs with sensorized fingertips, see **Supplemental Tables 1 and 2**). As a recent example, Controzzi et al. (140) developed the Mia hand (Prensilia, Italy), which is integrated with sensors that can measure normal and tangential forces at the fingertips. Sensorization of RPHs is a design requirement that should be considered as important as other functional requirements for hand prostheses, such as weight or dexterity. To improve RPH performance and sensor integration, next-generation RPHs should then be designed with their sensorization in mind. Information about hand state (joint position, forces, and touch) can also be beneficial to increase the dexterity of such hands, enabling automatic adjustments such as catching slipping objects (e.g., the bebionic3 hand) and shared-control strategies (see Section 4).

5.5.2. Improved stimulation strategies.

Biomimicry is one of the strongest trends in nerve stimulation strategies, as it promises to deliver biologically plausible stimulation patterns to evoke more natural sensations. Biomimetic approaches rely on bio-inspired models to compute the stimulation patterns, so new iterations of these models, based on the current experience in stimulation and neural recording, are needed to improve the quality of elicited sensations.

These model-based approaches permit simpler modulation strategies that increase the naturalness of sensations. Tan et al. (36), for example, proved that a sinusoidal modulation of the pulse width improved the naturalness of the sensation. Formento et al. (141) instead designed a strategy to activate asynchronously stimulated fibers, mimicking healthy neural activity; in their work, they replaced classical biphasic stimulation with a high-frequency burst

of pulses that slowly increased in amplitude, and confirmed their hypothesis in ex vivo experiments. Stimulation patterns that try to overcome the physical limits of present neural interfaces (as in 141) while paving the way for more natural evoked sensations also suggest the requirements for the future generation of neural interfaces and stimulators for sensory feedback: increase reaching without losing discrimination.

Biphasic: characterized by a two-phase, bidirectional wave with one positive phase and one negative phase

5.5.3. New computational architectures.

Neuromorphic architectures have the potential to represent a paradigm shift in the design of the control systems for bidirectional hand prostheses, going toward distributed systems and edge computing. Both sensor acquisition and stimulation can benefit from these trends because they lead to more reliable systems that scale well with the increase of sensors and stimulation active sites. If the next generation of neuromorphic hardware promotes portability and lower power consumption, it could lead to broader implementation and adoption of neuromorphic systems in bidirectional hand prostheses.

Many RPHs rely on advanced encoding and decoding algorithms implemented with neural networks (61), which are more computationally demanding than traditional approaches. It is interesting that even deep learning networks can be translated into spiking neural networks (142), possibly enabling full neuromorphic hardware encoding and decoding in future prostheses.

6. PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

Given the increasing complexity of RPHs that integrate both sensory and motor functionalities, it is important to have standardized tools to measure the efficacy of novel technologies (143). While designing custom experiments to evaluate a technology might be tempting, there is a crucial need for well-established assessment tools to enable comparisons of different approaches on a common basis.

Caregivers should assess how a technology solves patients' impairments (their body structures or functions), activity limitations (e.g., by improving their ability to grasp), and participation restrictions (e.g., by allowing them to participate in a sport). In addition, the impairment should be viewed not only from a biological perspective but also in terms of its psychosocial consequences; an effective RPH should promote autonomy and support the reintegration of the individual into society. The measurement of patients' health-related quality of life has now become a norm during the rehabilitation process (144). For example, the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Head (DASH) questionnaire (145) and its shorter, 11-item version, QuickDASH (146), provide self-administered measurements that focus on patients' symptoms and physical, social, and psychological aspects in populations with

Table 3 Clinical assessments for transradial amputees using robotic prosthetic hands

Name	Reference(s)	Measurement type	Clinically validated	Measurement					
				Quality of life	Embodiment	Grasp	Reach	Fine movement	Somatosensory feedback
QuickDASH	146	Questionnaire	X	X					Implicit
WHOQOL-BREF	147	Questionnaire	X	X					
Orthotics and Prosthetics User's Survey	143, 149	Questionnaire	X	X					Implicit
Box and Block Test	153, 154	Pick and place	X			X	X		Implicit
Nine Hole Peg Test	156, 157	Pick and place	X				X	X	Implicit
Clothespin Relocation Test	158	Pick and place							Implicit
Action Research Arm Test	159	Handling and manipulation of objects	X						Implicit
Southampton Hand Assessment Procedure	160	Handling and manipulation of objects	X						Implicit
Grasping Relative Index of Performance	138	Grasping				X			Explicit
Virtual Egg Test	128	Pick and place				X	X		Explicit
Prosthesis Efficiency and Profitability	138	Pick and place, manipulation				X	X		Explicit
Magnetic table task	163	Pick and place				X	X		Explicit
Cross Congruent Task	181	Psychometric			X				
Peripersonal test	174	Psychometric			X				

Abbreviations: QuickDASH, short version of the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Head questionnaire; WHOQOL-BREF, short version of the World Health Organization Quality of Life scale.

upper-extremity musculoskeletal conditions (**Table 3**). More generally, subjects' perception of their quality of life can be measured with the short version of the World Health Organization Quality of Life scale (WHOQOL-BREF) (147) or the Quality of Life Scale (QOLS) (148). The Orthotics and Prosthetics User's Survey (OPUS) (149) has also been used in upper-limb amputees (135). A recent study showed that long-term use of a sensorized prosthetic arm improved subjects' participation (e.g., skiing and fishing) (137); the authors performed semistructured interviews at patients' homes using a phenomenological approach to infer their experience with the prosthetic arm and to investigate the influence of a novel treatment within subjects' social groups (using an emic ethnographic approach) (150).

Another straightforward metric for evaluating the quality of a tool is patients' acceptance of the proposed protocol. Treatment adherence—measured by, for example, the number of sessions carried out by the patients per month, or the average session length—can help the experimenter develop tools that will be effectively used by the patients (150). In a study by Graczyk et al. (135) that compared the use of a prosthetic hand with and without tactile feedback, the subjects used a modified version of the OPUS Upper Extremity Functional Status module to report on a daily basis the difficulty of performing tasks such as brushing teeth or using a key in a lock.

When considering RPHs, assessment of the motor (or sensorimotor) functions is clearly essential. As described above, somatosensory feedback is crucial to performing a dexterous motor task (151); therefore, functional tests for motor tasks also implicitly evaluate the sensory feedback. In other words, high performance in, for example, a pick-and-place task using a bidirectional RPH indicates both an accurate motor decoding and sensory feedback. Other assessments [e.g., the Virtual Egg Test (152)] target the somatosensory feedback more explicitly. Here, we describe both types of measurements.

The Box and Block Test (153) is a common evaluation of unilateral gross manual dexterity (**Figure 3a**), where subjects must transport as many wooden blocks as possible from one compartment of a box to another within one minute. A modified version of this test with motion capture has been proposed (154) to evaluate eventual compensatory strategies of the shoulder or the trunk; a normative version using predefined positions of the blocks inside the box has also been proposed to facilitate kinematic analysis (155). The fine dexterity of fingers can be measured with the Nine Hole Peg Test, which involves the placing of small 1.3-cm-diameter dowels into nine holes (156). Variations of this test with motion tracking have also been proposed (157). The Clothespin Relocation Test (**Figure 3b**) measures both grasping and pronation/supination functions (158).

Figure 3 Examples of available assessment tools. (a) The standardized test equipment for the Box and Block Test includes a box with two compartments separated by a barrier and 150 2.5-cm colored blocks. The subject is asked to transfer as many blocks as possible from one from one compartment to the other in one minute. Panel adapted with permission from accsim instrumentos. (b) The Clothespin Relocation Test measures hand function (reaching, grasping, and wrist rotation). The measurement consists of the time it takes for the subject to move three clothespins from a horizontal to a vertical bar and then back (see, e.g., 182). Pannel adapted with permission from reference 182. (c) The Action Research Arm Test standard box is commercially available and contains different objects to assess grasp, grip pinch, and gross movement functions. Pannel reproduced with permission fromArat Kits.. (d) The Virtual Egg Test is a variation of the Box and Block Test where blocks are replaced by breakable objects. In this example, the plastic cubes have a magnetic fuse that breaks if the grasping force exceeds a certain threshold. Panel adapted with permission from Reference 128 (e) An audio–tactile interaction task has been used to measure the brain representation of the peripersonal space (the brain’s presentation of the space immediately around the body) (174). The test consists of a looming sound (perceived as coming from far away and moving toward the amputated hand) and a vibrator placed on the subject’s stump that is triggered when the sound is perceived to be at different distances from the subject (D1 to D5). The position where the presence of the sound facilitates the perception of the vibrator (reaction time) is used a proxy for the peripersonal space limit (*dashed line*).

The Action Research Arm Test (**Figure 3c**) is one of the most widely used measurements for upper-extremity (arm and hand) functions (159). It assesses four basic movements: grasp, grip, pinch, and gross movements of extension and flexion at the elbow and shoulder. Various sized and shaped objects from daily living (a cup, a washer, etc.) are used for the test, which provides a broad overview of patients' improvement in the activity and impairment domains. Finally, the Southampton Hand Assessment Procedure uses a set of abstract objects and activities of daily living with tasks specifically developed to assess the effectiveness of upper-limb prostheses (160).

These evaluations are used in rehabilitation and have been clinically validated (**Table 3**). Most of them were developed for neurological impairments (such as a stroke), multiple sclerosis, or spinal cord injuries and have been adapted for the evaluation of RPHs. While these well-established evaluations are essential, detailed investigation of RPHs—mainly when integrating sensory feedback capabilities—implies specific challenges that have been addressed in a series of tests introduced in recent years. These tests, although not yet clinically validated, are, in our opinion, of great interest.

The Grasping Relative Index of Performance measures the ability to control the desired force during grasping (138) independently from the control and feedback modalities. This measurement is based on the well-known Fitts' law, which states that the difficulty of a reaching task is given by the log of the ratio between the distance to the target and its size; in other words, the farther away and smaller a target is, the harder it is to reach it. Thumser et al. (161) argued that grasping is similar to pointing with the thumb and finger toward selected positions and defined the index of difficulty for grasping as the ratio of the object's weight to its hardness (where grasping a fragile object is analogous to a reaching a small target). Other assessments have been proposed to estimate object stiffness (138) and size discrimination (5); Risso et al. (162) investigated the contribution of vision, tactile feedback via intraneural stimulation, and visuo-tactile integration to estimate the size of a handheld object.

The magnetic table task (163) and the Virtual Egg Test (128) (**Figure 3d**) are variations of the Box and Block Test in which the blocks are replaced by magnetic cubes and breakable objects, respectively. Both have been used to evaluate the efficacy of different sensory encoding strategies (see 135 for the magnetic table task and 61 for the Virtual Egg Test). Finally, Prosthesis Efficiency and Profitability is an ad hoc measurement for prosthetics with sensory feedback to assess searching, reaching, grasping, manipulating, and decision-making during a foraging task (138).

Use of cognitive load during a sensorimotor task can give an indirect evaluation of the intuitiveness of a task: Do patients need to give their full attention to a particular movement, or are they able to perform it as part of a dual task? Subjects might be asked, for example, to perform a task while counting backward, finding words that start with a given letter, or visually following a moving target on a screen (for an example with a Virtual Egg Test, see 62). More direct measurement of the cognitive burden via electroencephalographic event-related potentials during human-machine interactions have also been proposed (164). Here, the subject must perform a specific task (the primary task) while detecting an auditory stimulus

(the secondary task), and the amplitude of the event-related potentials in response to the auditory stimulus then indicates the amount of dedicated attention to the secondary and primary tasks. Simply put, a small response to the auditory cue suggests more extensive attention to the primary task (165) and therefore a greater cognitive load.

The prolonged use of prosthetic limbs can reverse some of the effects of post-traumatic maladaptive plasticity, one of the most debilitating of which is phantom limb pain, a condition present in the majority of subjects with amputation (166). Phantom limb pain has a complex etiology that can be elicited by a multitude of factors, including nociceptive (neuroma hyperactivity), neuropathic (cortical reorganization), or psychogenic mechanisms. Numerous studies have shown that the use of prosthetics with sensory feedback significantly reduces phantom limb pain for upper-limb (36, 111, 113) and lower-limb (165) amputees. Typical measurements of pain are the McGill Pain Questionnaire (167), the Neuropathic Pain Symptom Inventory (168), and the Visual Analog Pain intensity scale, but it can also be measured with the DASH assessment (145) and the physical domain of the WHOQOL test.

Longitudinal experiments with amputee patients have demonstrated changes in body schema representation and embodiment of the prosthetic when tactile (61, 169) or proprioceptive (170) feedback is provided to the subject. A questionnaire-based measurement inspired by the rubber hand illusion (171) is often used. Tools for psychometrical measurement of the embodiment include a visuo-tactile integration task (172) and a cross-modal congruency task (173). A similar protocol using audio-tactile stimuli (174) revealed changes of the peripersonal space around the stump following prolonged use of a prosthetic limb (**Figure 3e**). In the same study, the authors used a tactile distance perception task in subjects' healthy and amputated arms to measure the perceived length of the remaining part of the upper limb and the homologous region of the healthy limb.

There is no single measurement that assesses all aspects of the use of an RPH. To evaluate the validity of novel technology, the experimenter should consider the multifaceted aspects of the impairment and subjects' biopsychosocial welfare, which is possible only via a series of tools, as presented in this section. In the case of prosthetics with sensory feedback, there is a lack of validated and well-established measurements, but several research groups are working to define adapted measurements, which might become the new norm in the future.

7. CONCLUSION

More than 20 years ago, remarkable results by a group of French surgeons for hand transplantation (7) had raised hopes for a future where grafting would be the norm and prosthetics eventually obsolete (175). However, not only has this prediction—unfortunately—not yet come to pass, but also the adoption of new RPH technologies has been slower than expected. As such, RPHs are still a field of active research. Significant efforts have been made to reduce their price and weight, improve their aesthetics and anthropomorphism, increase the robustness and accuracy of their motor intention decoding, and provide natural and

accurate somatosensory feedback. We have proposed here an outline of possible iterations of RPHs for the next few years and for 5–10 years in the future.

In our view, there could soon be a broader integration of simple somatosensory feedback using mature implantable techniques, such as cuff electrodes. Motor decoding using machine learning and shared-control algorithms could permit continuous command of single fingers and broader sets of grasps. Ultimately, the next generation of prosthetics could use more advanced soft implantable electrodes, which could enable more sophisticated sensory encoding (proprioception, temperature perception, touch perception, and nociception) and motor decoding using, for example, deep learning techniques. But to reach this goal, the field must tackle significant challenges related to system integration, electronic miniaturization, computational power, surgical procedure, electrode robustness, the robotic hand itself, and the encoding of somatosensory information.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

SM holds shares of Sensars Neurotechnology aiming at developing “bionic” limbs for amputees. The other authors declare no competing interests.

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